

METHODS OF ORGANIZING STUDENT ACTIVITY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Anatisation: Proper organization of the lesson in the classes of elementary school pupils is the priority task of the pedagogue, and the effective use of the methods of carrying out the activities of the pupils ensures the meaningful organization of the lesson.

Key words. Pupils, methods of activity management, frontal, rotational, continuous-connecting, individual, group, physical education lesson, part of the lesson.

By management of pupils' activities, we understand the method of organizing physical exercises according to the teacher's plan during training.

In the process of education, it is understood that physical education teachers organize the activities of pupils in physical education classes.

Let's see what methods of pupil activity management are used in physical education classes in primary grades:

1. The frontal method of organizing the pupil's activity means that all the pupils in the group perform the exercise individually together with the teacher to solve the same task. The advantage of this methodology is that all pupils are equally involved in the exercise and they are occupied individually, high density is achieved in the lesson (training), and the speed, intensity and standard of the load are the same for everyone. This methodology is mainly used in the preparatory and final parts of the lesson, in mastering and improving new material, and mostly in training with elementary school pupils.

2. method of continuous organization of pupils' activities. Without explanations of the order of performing the exercise, adapting the methodical instructions to the rhythm of the movement, without stopping the group to correct mistakes, it is manifested in the way of fully performing the movement activity in order to achieve high intensity. The advantage of this methodology is to achieve the same level of loading, its size and intensity for all pupils in the group (regardless of their physical fitness). This creates an opportunity to evaluate the general physical fitness of the pupils of the class and group, especially for the pupils themselves, to compare and compare the level of their movement capabilities in relation to their peers. It is mainly used in the preparatory and final parts of the lesson, as well as in the main part of the lesson, when mastering new material.

3. The content of the method of dividing the study group (class) into groups is based on the physical development, physical fitness, variety of tasks set in the lesson, and the necessary equipment to solve it, dividing a large group of pupils into small, is to divide into small groups. This methodology is mainly used in the main part of the lesson. The method of organizing the pupil's activities and dividing them into groups creates an opportunity to take into account their physical development and physical fitness during the educational process. This, in turn, makes the training process more effective, takes into account physical capabilities, and saves time spent on the educational process. Each group is directed to solve an independent, separate task with the teacher's assignment. This methodology puts the responsibility of the teacher, who is able to perform the task of leading a group, who is prepared in advance, knows the techniques of the subject, and prepares the group activist.

4. The methodology of individual organization of pupil activities is mainly used in the lessons of repeating the topics of the academic year, academic quarter, and sections of the State Standard program. Individual organization of pupils' activities requires pupils to acquire certain theoretical and practical knowledge in a technical way, to be able to ensure the safety of themselves and their teammates, to be able to show the exercise and, most importantly, to be mastered, the educational material being introduced, strengthened and improved, the exercise technique taught in advance for the pupils must be familiar material. In addition, in some classes, pupils are assigned tasks from topics or exercises that they have not mastered during the academic year. It is recommended to use this method mainly in classes conducted with pupils of middle and high school age.

5. Organization of the pupil's activity through the method of performing exercises in a circle, mainly with pupils of upper classes, after learning the planned educational material, moving from one exercise to another, at the teacher's command (signal), without a signal after performing the exercise, it is organized in the way of switching to another device in order to change the place. The effectiveness of this methodology is that time is saved, all pupils are busy, they develop the need for independent work and instructor skills.

This method is widely used in work with pupils of all levels of educational institutions, especially in introducing educational material.

The individual method consists in the fact that each pupil performs an exercise, and the rest watch him. This method is used in final lessons. This allows the teacher to conclude after the completion of each exercise, to attract the attention

of children to better performance of the exercise, shortcomings and mistakes, which is very important in terms of education and upbringing.

The methods of organizing pupils' activities in the lesson depend on the tasks, conditions, number of pupils and their readiness. In addition, the use of different methods increases pupils' interest in the lesson and the effectiveness of the lesson.

Looking at the above methods, each method has its own purpose. We use the appropriate method depending on the goal we are trying to achieve.

Primary school pupils use a more frontal approach, through which pupils are taught to work together, understand each other, and quickly overcome their shortcomings.

We organize the lesson in primary classes in an effective and interesting way by using the previously discussed methods correctly and effectively.

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